

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 149

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 149

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 149:1 ¹Praise ²the LORD! Sing to the LORD a ^anew song, <i>And</i> His praise ^bin the congregation of the godly ones. ² Let Israel be glad in ^ahis Maker; Let the sons of Zion rejoice in their ^bKing. ³ Let them praise His name with ^adancing; Let them sing praises to Him with ^btimbrel and lyre. ⁴ For the LORD ^atakes pleasure in His people; He will ^bbeautify the afflicted ones with salvation.</p> <p>Psa. 149:5 Let the ^agodly ones exult in glory; Let them ^bsing for joy on their beds. ⁶ <i>Let</i> the ^ahigh praises of God <i>be</i> in their ¹mouth, And a ^btwo-edged ^csword in their hand, ⁷ To ^aexecute vengeance on the nations And punishment on the peoples, ⁸ To bind their kings ^awith chains And their ^bnobles with fetters of iron, ⁹ To ^aexecute on them the judgment written; This is an ^bhonor for all His godly ones. ¹Praise ²the LORD!</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Psa. 149:1</p> <p style="text-align: center;">חָדָשׁ תִּהְיֶה לְתוֹ בְּקִהְלֵ חַסִּידִים : ² יִשְׁמַח יִשְׂרָאֵל בְּעֲשׂוֹ בְּנֵי-צִיּוֹן יִגִּילוּ בְּמִלְכָם : ³ יִהְלְלוּ שְׁמוֹ בְּמִחּוֹל בַּתֶּחֱ וְכִזְוֹר יִזְמְרוּ-לוֹ : ⁴ כִּי-רוֹצֵחַ יִהְיֶה בְּעַמּוֹ יִפְאֵר עֲנָוִים בִּישׁוּעָה : ⁵ יִעֲלֶזּוּ חַסִּידִים בְּכִבּוֹד יְרֻנְנוּ עַל- מִשְׁכְּבוֹתָם : ⁶ רוֹמְמוֹת אֵל בְּגִרוֹנָם וְחָרָב פִּיפְיוֹת בְּיָדָם : ⁷ לַעֲשׂוֹת נִקְמָה בַּגּוֹיִם תּוֹכַחַת בַּל-אֲמִים : ⁸ לְאַסֵּר מַלְכֵיהֶם בַּזְּנָקִים וְנִכְבְּדֵיהֶם בְּכַבְּלֵי בַרְזֶל : ⁹ לַעֲשׂוֹת בָּהֶם מִשְׁפָּט כְּתוּב הִרְרָה הוּא לְכָל-חַסִּידָיו תִּהְלְלוּ- יְהוָה :</p>

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References

Psalm 149:1

¹Or *Hallelujah!*

²Heb *YAH*

^aPs 33:3

^bPs 35:18; 89:5

Psalm 149:2

^aPs 95:6

^bJudg 8:23; Ps 47:6; Zech 9:9

Psalm 149:3

^a2 Sam 6:14; Ps 150:4

^bEx 15:20; Ps 81:2

Psalm 149:4

^aJob 36:11; Ps 16:11; 35:27; 147:11

^bPs 132:16; Is 61:3

Psalm 149:5

^aPs 132:16

^bJob 35:10; Ps 42:8

Psalm 149:6

¹Lit *throat*

^aPs 66:17

^bHeb 4:12

^cNeh 4:17

Psalm 149:7

^aEzek 25:17; Mic 5:15

Psalm 149:8

^aJob 36:8

^bNah 3:10

Psalm 149:9

¹Or *Hallelujah!*

²Heb *YAH*

^aDeut 7:12; Ezek 28:26
^bPs 112:9; 148:14

Targum

Psa. 149:1 Sing in the presence of the LORD a new psalm; his praise is in the assembly of the pious. ² They of the house of Israel will rejoice in their maker; the children of Zion will exult in their kings. ³ They will praise his name with dances, with drums and harps they will make music to him. ⁴ For the pleasure of the LORD is in his people; he will glorify the humble with redemption. ⁵ The pious will revel in glory; they will meditate upon their beds. ⁶ The psalms of God are in their throats, and in their hands like a two-edged sword. ⁷ To wreak vengeance on the Gentiles, rebuke among the nations. ⁸ To bind their kings with chains, and their nobles with fetters of iron. ⁹ To execute on them the judgment written in the Torah; this is glory for all his pious ones. Hallelujah!

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalmist informs us that the praise Psalms are only the beginning of what must be a continuous development of praises for the LORD. It is the perpetual destiny of Israel to praise the LORD. Every new generation meets new challenges and dilemmas. The LORD provides Divine assistance for the solving of any problem.

Notes on this Psalm

Praise the LORD in everything. It is that simple.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

